

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Assessing the oxidation of imidacloprid insecticide through the Cu(II)/PMS homogeneous process

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Fig. S1 Chemical structure of imidacloprid (IMD) insecticide - $C_9H_{10}ClN_5O_2$ and MW: $255.662 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$.

The ion composition and some physicochemical characteristics of tap water and simulated can be observed below.

Table S1 Chemical composition of tap water

Parameters	Experimental values
pH	6.14 – 6.20 (21.6 °C)
Conductivity / mS cm ⁻¹	32 μS cm ⁻¹ (21.2 °C)
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)	0.0
[Na ⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	1.85
[K ⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	2.96
[Mg ²⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	1.47
[Ca ²⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	2.61
[Br ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	5.32
[Cl ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	0.58
[SO ₄ ²⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	0.28

The amount of detected chlorine species (measured as OCl⁻) was 12.8 μmol L⁻¹

Text S1

Simulated municipal wastewater (SMWW)

The composition of SMWW, employed as a model for a secondary effluent matrix, was prepared following the methodology outlined by Sánchez-Montes et al. [1], as well as receipts described in Zhang *et al.* [2] and in APHA Standard Methods [3] with modifications. The following chemicals were used:

i) inorganics salts: NaHCO₃ (96 mg L⁻¹), MgSO₄ (60 mg L⁻¹), NaCl (580 mg L⁻¹), and K₂HPO₄ (7.0 mg L⁻¹), CaSO₄·2H₂O (60 mg L⁻¹) and (NH₄)₂SO₄ (23.6 mg L⁻¹), KCl (4 mg L⁻¹).

ii) organic matter: beef extract (1.8 mg L⁻¹), peptone (2.7 mg L⁻¹), humic acid (4.2 mg L⁻¹), sodium lignin sulfonate (2.4 mg L⁻¹), sodium lauryl sulphate (0.9 mg L⁻¹), tannic acid (4.2 mg L⁻¹) and acacia gum powder (4.7 mg L⁻¹).

Table S2 Physicochemical parameters of SMWW effluent

Parameters	Experimental values
pH	7.43 – 7.50 (21.6 °C)
Conductivity / mS cm ⁻¹	1,309 μS cm ⁻¹ (20.8 °C)
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)*	2.76 ±0.33

Text S2

Chromatographic conditions and mass spectrometry analyses for elucidation of IMD oxidation byproducts

The collected samples at varying treating times were analyzed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity II Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatograph (UHPLC – from Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Chromatographic separation was performed using a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Agilent, USA). The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid solution (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B). The chromatographic gradient used was as follows: 0-2 min, 20% B; 2.1-2.5 min, from 20 to 50% B; 2.5-7.0 min, from 50%-90% B. Column oven and autosampler temperatures were both set to 25 °C. The mobile phase flow and injection volume were 0.40 mL·min⁻¹ and 0.20 μL, respectively.

Mass spectra were obtained using an Agilent 6545B Q-ToF MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface and operated in the positive ion mode using a capillary voltage that varied from 2.0 to 3.0 kV. Table S3 shows the parameter values used during MS experiments that were optimized for the IMD standard.

Table S3 Q-ToF MS parameter values

Parameter	Value
Desolvation gas flow rate	10 L min ⁻¹
Gas temperature	250 °C
Nebulizer pressure	30 psi
Sheath gas temperature	275 °C
Sheath gas flow rate	10 L min ⁻¹
Nozzle voltage	115 V
Fragmentor voltage	60 V
Skimmer voltage	30 V
Octopole RF peak voltage	250 V
Collision energy	2 to 5 V

Molecular ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode. Data were collected in a range of 50 to 600 Da, with a sweep rate of 3.0 spectrum s⁻¹ and processed by MassHunter Workstation Software, version B.08.00.

Text S3

The determination of short-chain carboxylic acids was carried out using HPLC. This involved the use of a Rezex™ ROA-H column (300 mm × 7.8 mm i.d., 8 μm particle size, from Phenomenex®) as the stationary phase and a solution of 2.5 mmol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ as the mobile phase, with a flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. The identification of carboxylic acids was achieved by comparing their retention times with those of standards that had been previously analyzed. The volume injected, the detection wavelength, and the column temperature were set at 25 μL, 210 nm, and 23 °C respectively.

The analysis of inorganic ions was performed using HPLC with a conductivity detector (Shimadzu CDD-10A SP). For the determination of anions, a Shodex SI-52 4E column was used as the stationary phase at 45 °C, and a 3.6 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂CO₃ solution was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹. This analysis utilized a chemical suppressor system (Thermo Scientific™ ACRS 500) that pumped a regenerating solution of 3.6 mmol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ at a rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹. In terms of cation determination, a Shodex YS-50 column was used as the stationary phase at 40 °C, and a mixture of 4.0 mmol L⁻¹ oxalic acid and 6.0 mmol L⁻¹ tartaric acid solution was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹, without the use of the suppressor system.

Text S4

Chromatographic and mass spectrometry conditions for elucidation of DMPO oxidation byproducts

To determine the main oxidation byproducts resulting from DMPO oxidation by unknown radical species, UHPLC analyses were carried out using a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Agilent, USA) as stationary phase. The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid solution (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B). A gradient elution mode at 0.350 mL min⁻¹ was used to separate the main products according to the following sequence: 0-1 min, 5% B; 1-10 min, 95% B; 10-10.1 min, 95-5% B; and 10.5-13 min, 5% B. The injection volume, column, and autosampler temperatures were set to 1.0 μL and 35 °C, respectively. Identification of main byproducts through mass spectrometry was performed using an Agilent 6545B Q-ToF MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface, operated in positive ion mode using a capillary voltage of 2.0 kV. The desolvation gas flow and gas flow in the cone were 11 and 10 L min⁻¹, respectively. For the mass confirmation of the detected byproducts, the collision energies ranged from 5 V to 16 V. Other variables such as source temperature, fragmentation voltage, skimmer voltage, and nozzle voltage were set to 300 °C, 40 V, 35 V and 225 V, respectively. Molecular and fragment ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode. Data collected were analyzed ranging from 50 to 600 Da and processed by the MassHunter Workstation Software version B.08.00 (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA).

DMPO oxidation by unknown radical species were performed using 10 mL of deionized H₂O with pH adjusted to 8 using a 125 mmol L⁻¹ NaOH solution. In a typical experiment, 1.5 mg of PMS (corresponding to 500 μmol L⁻¹ of PMS) was transferred to a 20 mL glass vial. Then, 10 mL of ultrapure H₂O (pH 8 using 22 μL of a 125 mmol L⁻¹ NaOH solution) and 63 μL of a 2000 μmol L⁻¹ CuSO₄ solution were added to the flask to start the reaction under vigorous stirring. After 1 min reaction, 5 mL of the reaction mixture was extracted and 125 μL of a 4 mol L⁻¹ DMPO solution (final concentration of 100 mmol L⁻¹) were added to the remaining 5 mL. The resulting mixture was left under stirring for an additional 1 min. After this time, 200 μL of sample were collected and analyzed.

Table S4 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) obtained during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using Cu(II) ions at distinct PMS concentrations.

[PMS] ₀ (μmol L ⁻¹)	$k_{1st} / 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R ²
250	4.4 ±0.9	0.93 ±0.01
500	11.8 ±0.9	0.95 ±0.01
1000	23 ±2	0.92 ±0.01

Conditions: 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark. Mean values and error refer to two repetitions.

Table S5 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) obtained during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using Cu(II) ions at distinct pH values.

pH	$k_{1st} / 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R ²
8	11.8 ±0.9	0.95 ±0.01
9	15.3 ±0.6	0.985 ±0.006
10	60 ±10	0.96 ±0.01

Conditions: 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark. Mean values and error refer to two repetitions.

Fig. S2 a) IMD fraction and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) during peroxydisulfate (PDS) and peroxymonosulfate (PMS) activation by Cu(II) ions. Conditions: $[\text{Cu(II)}] = 800 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ ($12.5 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), $[\text{Oxidant}] = 500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{IMD}] = 50 \text{mg L}^{-1}$, 100 mL of solution using 10mmol L^{-1} of $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (pH 8-10) or KH_2PO_4 (pH 7) as buffer at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table S6 Retention time, main detected intermediates (m/z) and error of the main detected byproducts resulting from IMD oxidation by radical species resulting from PMS activation using Cu(II) ions.

#	Product	t_r (min)	ESI mode			
			m/z	Attribution (ESI+)	Error (ppm)	Ref.
1	IMD	6.785	256.0569	[M+H] ⁺	-10.5444	-
			209.0567	[M+H-NO ₂] ⁺		
			175.0962	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl] ⁺		
			128.0247	[M+H-HNO ₂ -C ₃ H ₄ N ₃] ⁺		
			84.0550	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl-C ₃ H ₂ N] ⁺		
2	P1	6.092	230.0418	[M+H] ⁺	-9.1286	[4,5]
			186.0422	[M+H-N ₂ O] ⁺		
			169.0151	[M+H-N ₂ O-NH ₃] ⁺		
			149.0837	[M+H-N ₂ O-Cl] ⁺		
			148.0730	[M+H-NO ₂ -Cl] ⁺		
			141.0201	[M+H-N ₂ O-NH ₃ -CO] ⁺		
			126.0094	[M+H-CH ₂ CIN ₄ O ₂] ⁺		
			107.0589	[M+H-NO ₂ -Cl-CH ₃ N ₂] ⁺		
3	P2	6.141	272.0518	[M+H] ⁺	-8.0866	[4,6–9]
			228.0518	[M+H-N ₂ O] ⁺		
			227.0486	[M+H-NO ₂] ⁺		
			225.0515	[M+H-HNO ₂] ⁺		
			210.0406	[M+H-N ₂ O-H ₂ O] ⁺		
			191.0909	[M+H-NO ₂ -Cl] ⁺		
			100.0496	[M+H-NO ₂ -Cl-C ₆ H ₅ N] ⁺		
4	P3	6.391	288.0463	[M+H] ⁺	-10.7620	[4,5,7–12]*
			244.0462	[M+H-N ₂ O] ⁺		
			241.0463	[M+H-HNO ₂] ⁺		
			226.0357	[M+H-N ₂ O-H ₂ O] ⁺		
			207.0856	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl] ⁺		
			189.0752	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl-H ₂ O] ⁺		
			169.0148	[M+H-HNO ₂ -H ₂ O-C ₂ H ₃ N ₂] ⁺		
5	P4	7.114	157.9985	[M+H] ⁺	-11.3923	[4,6,7,13]
			139.9865	[M+H-OH] ⁺		
			122.0220	[M+H-Cl] ⁺		
			111.9933	[M+H-OH-Cl] ⁺		
			78.0336	[M+H-Cl-COOH] ⁺		

Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹, 800 µg L⁻¹Cu(II), 500 µmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

*In Ref. [7], the second hydroxyl group was located at a different position.

Fig. S3 a) Extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) and MS/MS spectra of the main detected byproducts (4 in total) resulting from IMD oxidation by reactive oxygen species resulting from PMS activation using Cu(II) ions: **b)** IMD, **c)** P1, **d)** P2, **e)** P3 and **f)** P4. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S4 Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates showed in **Table S6**: **a)** IMD (m/z 256.0570), **b)** P1 (m/z 230.0418), **c)** P2 (m/z 272.0513), **d)** P3 (m/z 288.0456) and **e)** P4 (m/z 157.9993) [5,14]. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S4 (*continuation*) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates showed in **Table S6**: **a)** IMD (m/z 256.0570), **b)** P1 (m/z 230.0418), **c)** P2 (m/z 272.0513), **d)** P3 (m/z 288.0456) and **e)** P4 (m/z 157.9993) [5,14]. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Table S7 Toxicity classification for aquatic life according to the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS)*.

Toxicity range / mg L⁻¹	Classification
$LC_{50} \leq 1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$	Very toxic
$LC_{50} > 1 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ but $\leq 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$	Toxic
$LC_{50} > 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ but $\leq 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$	Harmful
$LC_{50} > 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$	Not harmful

*Available at:

https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/danger/publi/ghs/ghs_rev07/English/ST_SG_AC10_30_Rev7e.pdf

Fig. S5 a) Total ion chromatogram (TIC) and Extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) of the main detected byproducts resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation using Cu(II) ions. **Conditions:** 50 mg L^{-1} IMD, $800 \text{ }\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Cu(II), $500 \text{ }\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ and $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Table S8 Retention time and main fragment ions detected during reaction of DMPO with reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation using Cu(II) ions.

#	Product	t_r (min)	ESI mode		
			m/z	Attribution (ESI+)	Error (ppm)
1	DMPO/2OH	1.125	148.0966	[M+H] ⁺	-1.3504
			130.0856	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			115.0750	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			97.0649	[M+H-NH ₂ OH-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			90.0569	[M+H-H ₂ O-CH ₂ (CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	
			70.0226	[M+H-2H ₂ O-CH ₂ (CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	
			69.0698	[M+H-(OH) ₂ CH ₂ OH] ⁺	
2	DMPO	2.751	114.0915	[M+H] ⁺	1.7529
			97.0810	[M+H-OH] ⁺	
			82.0660	[M+H-OH-CH ₃] ⁺	
			81.0702	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			72.0449	[M+H-CH(CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	
			55.0549	[M+H-NH ₂ OH-C ₂ H ₂] ⁺	
3	DMPO/OH	3.926	130.0865	[M+H] ⁺	1.5374
			115.0940	[M+H-CH ₃] ⁺	
			98.0675	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			88.0755	[M+H-C ₃ H ₆] ⁺	
			69.0702	[M+H-CH ₃ NO ₂] ⁺	
			55.0542	[M+H-C ₂ H ₅ NO ₂] ⁺	
4	2DMPO/O-3H	4.821	241.1559	[M+H] ⁺	4.9760
			224.1558	[M+H-OH] ⁺	
			209.1290	[M+H-OH-CH ₃] ⁺	
			191.1191	[M+H-OH-CH ₃ -H ₂ O] ⁺	
			178.1234	[M+H-OH-CH ₃ -H ₂ O-HNO] ⁺	
			165.1519	[M+H-OH-CH ₃ -H ₂ O-C ₂ H ₄] ⁺	
			128.1074	[M+H-OH-CH ₃ -HNO-C ₄ H ₅] ⁺	
			114.0919	[M+H-OH-CH ₃ -HNO-C ₅ H ₆] ⁺	
			94.0652	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₀ NO ₂ -OH] ⁺	

Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹, 800 μg L⁻¹Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Table S8 (*continuation*) Retention time and main fragment ions detected during reaction of DMPO with reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation using Cu(II) ions.

5	2DMPO/-H	4.414	227.1763	[M+H] ⁺	3.9616
			209.1660	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			194.1551	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			177.1548	[M+H-H ₂ O-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			114.0927	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₂ NO] ⁺	
			96.0826	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₂ NO-OH] ⁺	
			81.0711	[M+H-H ₂ O-NH ₂ OH-C ₆ H ₁₀ N] ⁺	
			74.0602	[M+H-H ₂ O-C ₆ H ₁₀ N-CH ₂ (CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	
6	2DMPO/-3H	5.140	225.1609	[M+H] ⁺	4.8854
			207.1501	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			189.1402	[M+H-2H ₂ O] ⁺	
			175.1247	[M+H-2H ₂ O-CH ₃] ⁺	
			161.1080	[M+H-2H ₂ O-2CH ₃] ⁺	
			112.0759	[M+H-H ₂ O-C ₆ H ₈ N] ⁺	
			94.0662	[M+H-H ₂ O-C ₆ H ₁₁ NO] ⁺	
			69.0711	[M+H-H ₂ O-C ₆ H ₈ N-CH ₂ NO] ⁺	

Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹, 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S6 MS/MS spectra of the main detected byproducts resulting from the reaction resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation using Cu(II) ions: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S7 Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation using Cu(II) ions: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 800 μg L⁻¹, Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S7 (continuation) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation using Cu(II) ions: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S7 (continuation) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation using Cu(II) ions: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 800 μg L⁻¹ Cu(II), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ and 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S8 UV-vis spectra evolution over time after reaction between Cu(II) ions and PMS in the presence of periodate ions (IO_4^-). The highlighted wavelength is ascribed to the complex compound formed between Cu(III) and IO_4^- ions. **Conditions:** $[\text{Cu(II)}] = 2 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{PMS}] = 80 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$, $[\text{IO}_4^-] = 2 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$, using 20 mL of ultrapure H_2O at pH 8 and without buffer.

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